

Progress in the preparation of magnetic nanoparticles for applications in biomedicine

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Abstract

Magnetic nanoparticles are nowadays a powerful tool (material) inside the biomedicine field. Their unique magnetic properties and small size lead to the particles the ability to interact with biomolecules, cells and organs that make possible the diagnosis at early stages of the tumour and treatment of several diseases. Recent advances of the use of magnetic nanoparticles in biomedicine are strongly related with the enhancement of the structural (size, size distribution and shape) and magnetic properties (magnetic moment, initial susceptibility) of the particles. Also, new routes to tailor the surface in order to make the particles stable in water or conjugate with biomolecules such as peptides or DNA fragments have been developed. This review summarizes the progress that has occurred in this field during the last five years, from the synthesis of MNPs to the surface functionalization in order to use the particles as contrast agents or drug vehicles.

Keywords: magnetic nanoparticles, synthesis, surface modification

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1. Introduction

The combination of the magnetic properties at the nanometre scale of the magnetic nanoparticles and the high penetrability of the magnetic field along the human organs and tissues are the key factors of the explosion of these materials inside the biomedicine field (Pankhurst *et al.*, 2003). The shortening of the T2 relaxation time of the water molecules that surround the particles (Rosensweig, 2002), the heat-generating capacity when a ac field is applied (Weissleder *et al.*, 1995) and the possibility to vector (drive, deliver..) the particles inside the body (Arruebo *et al.*, 2007) (blood, veins) are used in medicine to design (tailor) platforms (systems) that has the ability of predict (diagnostic) and treat (cure) diseases (tumours). Each application requires some specific features and the design of a nanobject to use in biomedicine depends on several parameters. For example, for application in MRI, the magnitude of the contrast depends on the magnetic properties of the material (i.e. material, crystallinity, particle size) and hydrodynamic size (Jun *et al.*, 2008). The time of retention and clearance from the blood by the macrophages of the RES and the Kupfer cells depends on the organ/tissue to visualized and it's influenced by the hydrodynamic size and the chemistry of the surface (nature of the coating, surface groups, hydrophilicity) (Corot *et al.*, 2006). On the other hand, for drug delivery/release it's important to note that the effectiveness delivery/release depends on the magnetic moment of the nanovector used, the effective surface that the particles have to be loaded with the drug, the way of attach the drug (adsorption, encapsulation, covalent bond), surface chemistry and way to release the drug (change in temperature, pH electric charge, light, sound, magnetism...)(Sun *et al.*, 2008).

In a previous work we reviewed the different methods of preparing magnetic nanoparticles and the different pathways to coat/encapsulate the particles properly depending on

the application (Tartaj *et al.*, 2003). During the last five years other synthesis methods has gained in attention upon the conventional coprecipitation (Massart, 1981). This is the case of the decomposition of metal organic compounds (iron, cobalt nickel) at high temperature in organic media and in the presence of surfactants (oleic acid)(Rockenberger *et al.*, 1999; Sun and Zeng, 2002; Hyeon *et al.*, 2001) that produce (where) monodisperse and high crystalline particles (could be obtained). Due to its high crystallinity, these particles present saturation magnetization values close to the bulk ones(Roca *et al.*, 2006) and, as a consequence of that, these particles present high values of r_2 larger than the commercial agents(Lee *et al.*, 2007). However, this method presents the disadvantage of the insolubility of the particles in water due to the orientation of the hydrocarbon tails towards the solvent. In this case a further surface modification is necessary in order to transfer the particles into water. Other methods like hydrothermal synthesis (Daou *et al.*, 2006) and precipitation in a mixture of water/ethanol lead to particles around the monodomain/multidomain limit (Andres-Verges *et al.*, 2008), that's very important in order to obtain a high SAR (Specific Absorption Rate)(Goya *et al.*, 2008).

Suspensions of aggregate or individual magnetic nanoparticles are approved by the FDA for use in biomedicine. In concrete, superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles, in the form of maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), coated by dextran is being used as contrast agent in MRI(Corot *et al.*, 2006). During the last years, it has been proposed different materials to be used in biomedicine. For example, due to their higher magnetic moment, cobalt ferrite (CoFe_2O_4) nanoparticles synthesized by thermal decomposition and coated with DMSA has been proposed as T2 contrast agents(Lee *et al.*, 2007). Their relaxivity values (r_2) are larger comparing to those belonging to commercial iron oxide based contrast agents(Laurent *et al.*, 2008). In the same way, Fe particles synthesized by laser pyrolysis presents relaxivity values larger than commercial contrast agents(Bomati-Miguel *et al.*, 2005). However, due to their lack of chemical stability and trend to aggregation, surface must be passivated with oxygen converting into $\text{Fe}@ \gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ core shell structure. Perovskite nanoparticles of...have been recently proposed as nanoheaters to treat and cure tumoral cells. The tunable Curie temperature with the size and the composition of the perovskite could be a great advantage to switch off the heat source when the local temperature of the tumour reaches the desire value. Nanoporous carbon with superparamagnetic particles prepared by spray pyrolysis have presented high values of specific surface(Fuertes and Tartaj, 2007).

2. Synthesis of magnetic nanoparticles

Magnetic NPs for biomedical applications must fit the specific characteristics required. The first requirement is often superparamagnetism at the application temperature (normally body temperature, 37 °C) so the range of the nanoparticle size must be of few nanometers (2-30 nm).

Thermal decomposition of metal organic compounds

As it was described in the Introduction, the thermal decomposition method has gained in attention during the last years. This method presents several advantages over conventional methods like the precise control of the size and shape of the particles, the narrow size distribution that's very important in order to have all the particles contributing to the same effect and the high crystallinity that increase the magnetic moment(Roca *et al.*, 2006).

During the last years, several groups showed that the change on the amount and nature of the precursor, solvent, surfactant are the most critical factors that affects the size of the nanoparticles. The most common precursors used are iron pentacarbonyl (Hyeon *et al.*, 2001) and iron acetylacetonate(Sun and Zeng, 2002). $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ is a volatile compound that is usually injected in the organic solvent in the present of surfactants at high temperatures obtaining particles of around 10 nm depending of the surfactant used. A second step is required in order to oxidized completely to $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ using $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{NO}$. In the case of the $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$, the precursor is heated up from room temperature up to 200 °C in order to form the Fe-oleic acid complex and further heating to reflux(Sun *et al.*, 2004). The formation of the Fe-oleic acid is a critical step in the final size of the particles and the groups of T. Hyeon and X. Peng synthesized $\text{Fe}(\text{oleate})_3$

starting from sodium oleate and FeCl_3 (Park *et al.*, 2004) and oleic acid, sodium hydroxide and FeCl_3 respectively (Jana *et al.*, 2004). With iron oleate as precursor it was possible to synthesize particles up to 22 and 50 nm. Increasing the boiling point of the solvent or decreasing the coordination capacity has been shown that are also valid techniques to obtain larger particles due to the increase in the monomer capacity. For example, using $\text{Fe}(\text{oleate})_3$ as precursor the particle size increases from 5 nm using 1-hexadecane (b. p. 274 °C) to 22 nm using trioctylamine (b. p. 365 °C) (Park *et al.*, 2004). The variation of the particle size with the surfactant depends on the Fe:surfactant relation and the bond strength of the polar group of the surfactant with the Fe atoms of the surface. The group of V. L. Colvin studied the influence of different molar relations between Fe and oleic acid and the particle size increased from 7 to 28 nm when the Fe: oleic acid relation was 1:3 and 1:8 respectively (Yu *et al.*, 2004). However, the group of Z. Li showed the opposite relation when a polymer was used (Li *et al.*, 2005), decreasing the particle size because the polymer inhibits the growth. An example of the influence of using different surfactants was shown by the group of J. W. Cheon (Cheon *et al.*, 2004). Particles synthesized starting from $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ in o-dichlorobenzene increase in size from 6 to 12 nm when the surfactant used was TOPO (trioctylphosphine oxide) or dodecylamine. In this case, the higher coordination capacity of TOPO affects the growth of the particles limiting their size. Another possibility is growing up particles synthesized before in a technique that is called “seeding up”. With this technique it’s possible to grow particles of 6 nm to 8, 10 and 20 nm using $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ as precursor and phenyl ether or benzyl ether as solvents (Sun *et al.*, 2004). The group of T. Hyeon obtained particles of $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ controlling the growth from 6 to 13 nm in one nanometer step (Park *et al.*, 2005).

The shape of the particles can be controlled principally by the type or amount of the surfactants, the concentration of the precursors and the addition of some impurities. For example, when the concentration of the precursors is low, the growth process is thermodynamically controlled and the particle shape tends to be spherical (Casula *et al.*, 2006). However, if the concentration of the precursors is high, the growth of the particles is kinetically controlled and the particles growth by the high surface energy face giving particles with cube or tetrahedral shape. For example, the presence of dodecylamine in octyl ether when $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ is injected produce mixture of triangles, spheres and diamonds (Cheon *et al.*, 2004). The 10-fold increase of dodecylamine results in in particles with hexagonal shape. When the precursor changed to $\text{FeO}(\text{OH})$ or $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ the increase of surfactant:precursor ratio produces particles with cubic shape (Yin *et al.*, 2004).

Probably, the most relevant result during the last years related with the structure is the formation of hollow structures like spheres, cubes or frames using Molten salts like sodium oleate that produce empty cavities by Kirkendall effect (Kim *et al.*, 2007; A. Cabot *et al.*, 2007).

In order to produce hydrophilic magnetic nanoparticles for biomedical applications using the thermal decomposition method, it was developed the direct synthesis in polar organic solvents in the presence of hydrophilic polymers or molecules. The group of M. Gao synthesized magnetite particles of 5 nm using $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ as precursor 2-pyrrolidone as coating and solvent (Li *et al.*, 2004). The resulting particles are coated by the molecules of the solvent. However, this coating is not sufficient to screen the dipolar interactions of the particles and added to the reaction in later studies mono and dicarboxylic-terminated PEG (Li *et al.*, 2005; Hu *et al.*, 2006). The group of E. Liu decomposed at high temperature $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ in triethyleneglicol obtaining particles of 8 nm stable in water (Wan *et al.*, 2007). Departing from an inorganic precursor, for example FeCl_3 , and PAA (polyacrylic acid) it’s possible to produce Fe_3O_4 particles coated with this polymer (Ge *et al.*, 2007). This reaction is catalized by NaOH and using diethyleneglicol as solvent. The group of D. Caruntu and C. O’Connor used quelates of Fe (chelate metal alkoxide complexes) that hydrolized at elevated temperature using as solvent the same chelating alcohols (D. Caruntu *et al.*, 2007). Although the synthesis of direct hydrophilic magnetic nanoparticles by thermal decomposition leads to iron oxide magnetic nanoparticles, nowadays (up to now, at the present) the size distribution and the long-time stability in water represents two main challenges of this method.

3. Surface modification

Coating of magnetic nanoparticles by surfactants like oleic acid difficult the transference and stabilization of the particles in water. During the last years, several attempts to transfer to aqueous media organic stable Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles synthesized by thermal decomposition. These methods can be classified depending on the coating nature (organic or inorganic).

Organic coatings

Tailoring the surface of the nanoparticles with organic molecules provide different moieties to the particles like carboxylic, amine, thiol or aldehyde groups. Three main different routes have been followed to provide an organic coating to the particles.

The first one is the ligand exchange reaction of the oleic acid with small multifunctional molecules. This easy and rapid reaction use ligands with two or more functional groups, one of them bonds to the nanoparticles with high coordination capacity (carboxylic, phosphate) and the others are able to stabilize the particles in aqueous media, normally by electrostatic repulsion. Examples of these molecules are dimercaptosuccinic acid(Jun *et al.*, 2005; Lee *et al.*, 2005), citric acid(Taboada *et al.*, 2007), mercapto 11-undecanoic acid(Bagaria *et al.*, 2006) and tetramethylammonium hydroxide(Salgueiriño-Maceira *et al.*, 2004) (see table X).

The modification of the double bond of the oleic acid has (posses) the advantage that there is no moment in which the nanoparticle surface is naked or the bound of the carboxylic group to the surface is not altered (modified). Recently appeared routes to completely oxidize this double bound by ozonolysis(Lee and Harris, 2006) or oxidation by KMnO_4 (Herranz *et al.*, 2008). In these two cases the oleic acid is broken in two parts and a carboxylic group appears at the end of the organic fragment attached to the nanoparticles.

The coating of the nanoparticles with polymers or encapsulation in liposomes assures the stability of the particles by steric repulsion (barrier) and delay the opsonization (prolongation of the circulation time in blood) when they are injected intravenously. However, the stability depends on the polymers nature, the proportion between the hydrophobic and hydrophilic monomers, molecular weight or conformation (Sun *et al.*, 2008). There are different ways to coat the particles with a polymer. The most used is the intercalation of polymers that have hydrophobic and hydrophilic part like Pluronics(Qin *et al.*, 2007; Jain *et al.*, 2005), cyclodextrines(Wang *et al.*, 2003) or block polymers(Smith *et al.*, 2006; Pellegrino *et al.*, 2004). Another strategy is doing an exchange of oleic acid with polymers that have functional groups affine to the nanoparticle surface. This exchange must be carried out in extreme conditions due to the high weight of the polymers(Zhang *et al.*, 2007; Narain *et al.*, 2007; Xie *et al.*, 2007). Although this route has been less used, the synthesis of magnetite nanoparticles in the presence of polymers is also possible(Hu *et al.*, 2006; Jiang and Kim, 2006; Belfield and Li, 2006). The bound of molecules to the magnetic particles that is able to initiate a polymerization via free radicals species like 3-bromopropionylester is another strategy that has been tested(Gravano *et al.*, 2005).

The encapsulation of magnetic nanoparticles inside liposome or forming micelles with phospholipids as surfactants intercalated between the oleic acid molecules forms magnetic colloids of few hundred nanometers(Tromsdorf *et al.*, 2007; Dubertret *et al.*, 2002). Although this route is a bit expensive, it's a good strategy in order to have aggregated particles with low recognition of the macrophages when they are injected.

Inorganic coatings

Inorganic coatings as silica, gold or semiconductors like quantum dots are the most used to their biocompatibility, chemical stability and facility to further functionalization steps.

Silica is inert, biocompatible (but no biodegradable) and posses hydroxyl groups that are ionized at pH 7 providing negative charge. The Stöber method is the most used to coat the particles with silica. This method consists on a hydrolytic process using TEOS(Aslam *et al.*, 2005; Kim *et al.*, 2006 (tetraethoxiorthosilicate) but is very difficult coat the particles

Table 1. Routes of transference to water of hydrophobic magnetite nanoparticles using inorganic coatings.

COATING	METHOD	EXAMPLES
SÍLICA	SOL/GEL PROCESS	TEOS
	LIGAND EXCHANGE	APS SILSESQUIOXANE
	REVERSE MICELLES	CICLOHEXANE/IGEPAL TRITON X-100/HEXANOL
GOLD	HETEROGENOUS NUCLEATION	Au on Fe ₃ O ₄ : Au (acet) ₂ Fe ₃ O ₄ on Au: Fe(CO) ₅
	BIFUNCTIONAL BRIDGE MOLECULE	HS(CH ₂) ₁₀ COOH
	REDUCTUON OF GOLD SALT	HAuCl ₄
QUANTUM DOTS	HETEROGENOUS NUCLEATION	CdSe

individually and composites are usually obtained. Another way is doing a ligand exchange between the oleic acid and APS(Aslam *et al.*, 2005) (3-amino propyltriethoxisilane) that add (functionalize) amine groups to the surface or a sisesquioxane(TMA-POSS)(Frankamp *et al.*, 2006). The most promising method is doing reverse micelles and hydrolize the TEOS inside the drops(Zhang *et al.*, 2008; Lu *et al.*, 2007).

Gold is an inert material and biocompatible because of the affinity biomolecules that posses thiol groups to the gold surface(Sun *et al.*, 2008). Also, it confers optical properties (surface plasmon) apart from the magnetic ones of the particles. With gold it's possible to obtain core-shell or dimer structures. The formation of core-shell structures can be carried out though the thermal decomposition of gold precursors as gold acetate(Wang *et al.*, 2005; Chiang and Chen, 2007) or reduction of HAuCl₄ in a mixture of water/chloroform and oleylamine(Choi *et al.*, 2006). The formation of dimmer structures is possible due to the heterogeneous nucleation of magnetite nanoparticles in the presence of Au that growth epitaxially(Yu *et al.*, 2005). Another strategy is using a bifunctional molecule with a thiol and carboxylic group to attach gold and magnetite particles(Lim *et al.*, 2007).

The formation of heterodimers or particles with core shell structure between magnetic particles and quantum dots leads to magnetic and luminescent colloids. These structures are formed by heterogeneous nucleation of the QDs on the magnetite particles(Kwon *et al.*, 2006; Gao *et al.*, 2007).

Functionalization

Because one main requirement to applicate the particles in biomedicine relies on avoiding the opsonization and increasing the circulation time in the blood they must be coated with an hydrophilic polymer like PEG or dextran. Most of the routes described before lead to aggregates of particles with a high hydrodynamic size or aggregates of particles embebbed in a polymer so frequently is better to carry out a fist step to transference to water using a ligand exchange reaction (DMSA, CTAB). In a second reaction the polymer is bonded to the surface functional groups of the particles. One example of this reaction is the formation of an amide bond between a carboxylic and a amine group with the aid of the carbodiimides and N-hydroxysuccinimide that act as catalyst(Tedder *et al.*, 1972; Quarta *et al.*, 2008). Another reaction that is very often used when amine groups are present at the particle surface is the

reaction between glutaraldehyde and the amines that creates aldehyde groups at the surface(Laurent *et al.*, 2008). The hydroxyl groups of silica are more reactive than those of carbohydrates and leads to condensation reactions. The bound between avidine or streptoavidin and biotin is the most energetic (stable, strongest) non covalent union(Shaiu *et al.*, 1993)

(attachment, join, bound). This reaction is very used to conjugate proteins, peptides, phospholipids and PEG.

Table 1. Routes of transference to water of hydrophobic magnetite nanoparticles using organic coatings.

COATING	METHOD	EXAMPLES
BIFUNCTIONAL MOLECULES	LIGAND EXCHANGE	DMSA, SILANE-PEG, CITRIC ACID, PHOSPHONATES, DOPAMINE, MERCAPTO-11-UNDECANOIC, 2-BROMO,2-METILPROPIÓNIC ACID, DENDRÍMERS, TMAOH.
DOUBLE BOUND OF OLEIC ACID	OXIDATION & BRAKE	O ₃ , KMnO ₄
POLYMERS	INTERCALATION	PLURONIC F-127, PMMA-PEO, ANHYDRIDE MALEIC-ALT-1-TETRADECENE, PAA+OCTYLAMINE PEI, CYCLODEXTRINES
	LIGAND EXCHANGE	PAA-PAH , PNIPAm-b-PNIPAm, HOOC-PEG-COOH
	SYNTHESIS OF PARTICLES IN THE PRESENCE OF POLYMERS	HOOC-PEG-COOH, ω-FUNCTIONALIZED POLYSTIRENES NORBORNANE
	POLYMERIZATION IN THE PRESENCE OF PARTICLES	2-BROMOPROPYONILESTHER(INICIATOR)
LIPOSOMES	MICELLES FORMATION	PEG-PE+PC
	ENCAPSULATION	DSPE-PEG(2000)-BIOTINE

4. Final remarks

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Tables

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